

Taurine inhibits apolipoprotein E4 aggregation

Anthony Legrand^{a,b,1} ,
Naina Verma^{a,b,d,1} ,
Aliaksandra Kursit^{a,b} ,
Josef Kucera^{b,d} ,
Petr Kouba^{a,e} ,
Stanislav Mazurenko^{a,b} ,
David Bednar^{a,b,**}

^a Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5, Brno 625 00, Czech Republic

^b International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, Pekarska 53, Brno 656 91, Czech Republic

^c Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5, Brno 625 00, Czech Republic

^d Research Centre for Applied Molecular Oncology, Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute, Zlutý kopec 7, Brno 656 53, Czech Republic

^e Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics, Czech Technical University in Prague, Jugoslavských partyzánů 1580/3, Dejvice, Praha 6, 160 00, Czech Republic

^f Center for Disease Neurogenomics, Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai, 1 Gustave L. Levy Pl, New York, NY 10029, USA

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ABSTRACT

Apolipoprotein E4 (ApoE4) is a major genetic risk factor in many neurodegenerative diseases, yet effective therapeutic strategies targeting its associated pathologies remain unresolved. The aggregation of ApoE4, a key pathological feature, is modulated by tramiprosate and its metabolite 3-sulfopropanoic acid. In this study, we provide mechanistic insights into how taurine, a close chemical analogue of tramiprosate, interacts with ApoE4 and may similarly modulate its aggregation behavior. Using an integrated approach, which included molecular dynamics simulations, static light scattering, mass spectrometry, and cerebral organoid models, we investigated the effects of taurine on ApoE4 aggregation. Our results indicate that taurine effectively prevents ApoE4 aggregation and exerts a partial disaggregating effect on pre-formed aggregates. Notably, taurine modulates molecular and cellular features associated with the ApoE4 isoform, shifting them toward patterns observed in the more benign ApoE3 isoform. These observations are consistent with effects similar to those reported for tramiprosate and 3-sulfopropanoic acid and suggest that taurine influences ApoE4-related molecular mechanisms, particularly in the context of the high-risk *ApoE4/E4* genotype.

1. Introduction

Human apolipoprotein E (ApoE) is a 34 kDa glycoprotein that was

initially isolated as a very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) from plasma. It is structured into an N-terminal 5-helix bundle (Fig. 1A), followed by a hinge region and a C-terminal membrane-anchoring domain (CTD) [1].

Abbreviations: A β , amyloid A β peptide; Abslog2FCH, absolute log fold change; AD, Alzheimer's Disease; ApoE, apolipoprotein E; CO, cerebral organoid; HDX-MS, hydrogen-deuterium exchange mass spectrometry; LBD, Lewy body dementia; LIE, linear interaction energy; NTR, non-treated; PD, Parkinson's disease; RFU, relative fractional uptake; SPA, 3-sulfopropanoic acid; Tau, Tau protein; TMP, tramiprosateTRN – taurine; VLDL, very low-density lipoprotein.

* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding authors at: Department of Experimental Biology and RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kamenice 5, Brno 625 00, Czech Republic.

*** Corresponding author at: International Clinical Research Center, St. Anne's University Hospital Brno, Pekarska 53, Brno 656 91, Czech Republic.

E-mail addresses: josef.sivic@cvut.cz (J. Sivic), hernychova@seznam.cz (L. Hernychova), 222755@muni.cz (D. Bednar), dasa.bohaciakova@med.muni.cz (D. Bohaciakova), zbynek@chemi.muni.cz (Z. Prokop).

¹ Shared first authors

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Fig. 1. Description of ApoE's N-terminal domain and small molecules used in this study. (A) The N-terminal domain of ApoE4 (22–165) is a 5-helix bundle. C112R mutation is highlighted in red. H: helix. HL1: small helix between H1 and H2. L: loop. (B) Structure of an ApoE4_{22–165} T-shaped dimer assembled from 2 monomers (PDB: 8AX8). The rest of the protein was not resolved experimentally and is thus absent from the final structure. Through this study, we refer to chains A and B as the horizontal and vertical protomers, respectively. (C) Molecular structure of tramiprosate (TMP), 3-sulfopropanoic acid (SPA), and taurine (TRN).

ApoE is involved in lipid metabolism as well as a variety of neurodegenerative diseases, such as macular degeneration, Alzheimer's Disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), and Lewy body dementia (LBD) [2,3]. ApoE is the key molecule for pathogenesis at various levels of biological systems, formulated in the so-called "ApoE Cascade Hypothesis". This hypothesis states that the biochemical and biophysical properties of ApoE impact a cascade of events at the cellular and systems levels, ultimately impacting aging-related pathogenic conditions, such as AD. However, such involvement vastly depends on which isoform is encoded in the patient's genome. In the case of AD and PD, ApoE2 is a protective factor, ApoE3 is neutral, and ApoE4 is a risk factor [4]. Previously, we described and compared ApoE3 and ApoE4 self-associating interfaces (Fig. 1B), and how tramiprosate (TMP) and its metabolite 3-sulfopropanoic acid (SPA) [5] can inhibit their formation (Fig. 1C). We highlighted the domino-like effect of the single mutation from ApoE3 to ApoE4, C112R, leading to multiple conformational changes propagating through the entire protein and modifying aggregation-prone interfaces, which could be then corrected using SPA. Additionally, we showed that cerebral organoids (COs) could endogenously metabolise TMP into SPA, and that such treatment stimulates neurogenesis, modifies cholesterol metabolism and the levels of AD-related proteins, and decreases MAP kinase signaling in COs with *ApoE4/E4* genotype.

Taurine (TRN) is a highly abundant brain metabolite, mainly detected in the central nervous system (Fig. 1C). The brain can produce taurine locally, but it also relies heavily on uptake from the blood. Its supplementation, usually through diet, is beneficial in the contexts of tissue and cell stress, inflammation and in many pathologies, such as intracerebral haemorrhage or hypertension [6]. TRN has a very similar structure to TMP, only differing by a single methylene group. While TMP is metabolized *in vivo* into SPA [5], TRN is obtained from cysteine and metabolized into dipeptides (e.g. glutamyltaurine), acyltaurines, and TRN-conjugated bile acids [7]. Finally, there is a clear correlation between decreased TRN levels in the brain, brain senescence, and the accumulation of phosphorylated protein Tau and Amyloid-beta (A β) peptide [8]. However, to the best of our knowledge, its putative interplay with ApoE in the context of neurodegeneration has never been addressed. Here, we combine *in silico*, *in vitro*, and *in vivo* cellular experiments to characterize the influence of TRN on ApoE aggregation and to evaluate its effects on COs.

2. Methods

2.1. System preparation and equilibration

The structure of TRN was constructed and minimized using Avogadro 2 [9]. As expected at pH 7.4, SPA was considered deprotonated on the sulfonate (SO_3^-) and protonated on the amine (NH_3^+) groups, with a net charge of 0. A minimization step was performed on those structures by the Auto Optimization Tool of Avogadro, using the UFF force field with the steepest descent algorithm [10]. The resulting structure was then submitted for further optimization and calculation of their partial atomic charges using Gaussian 09 [11], with the Hartree-Fock method and 6–31 G(d) basis set in vacuum. The antechamber module of AmberTools 16 [12] was used to extract the RESP charges of the ligand from the Gaussian output files. To prepare the PAR and RTF parameter files compatible with the CHARMM force field we used the SwissParam web server [13].

The three-dimensional structures of the N-terminal domain (NTD; 22–165) of ApoE3 and ApoE4 were obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (PDB ID 1BZ4 and 8AX8, respectively) [5,14]. PyMOL 2.3 (The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.3 Schrödinger, LLC.) was used to generate the T-shaped dimer from that structure with the symmetry information contained in the original PDB files. Both protomer chains of the dimers were renamed as A and B (Fig. 1B). The crystallographic water molecules were maintained.

The following steps were performed with the High Throughput Molecular Dynamics (HTMD) scripts [15]. The protein was protonated with PROPKA 2.0 at pH 7.4 [16]. Each protein was simulated free or with an excess of TRN ligands. The free protein was solvated with a cubic box of TIP3P water with the edges at least 25 Å away from the protein atoms, using the solvate module of HTMD [17]. Using a Python script in the preparation protocol of HTMD, the protein with ligands was prepared by adding 100 molecules of TRN randomly placed on a sphere with a radius of 3 Å further from any atom of the protein, and at least 5 Å away from each other; the system was then solvated with a cubic box of TIP3P water with the edges at least 5 Å away from the ligand atoms. Na^+ and Cl^- ions were added to neutralize the charge of the system and get a final salt concentration of 0.1 M. The topology of the system was built using the `htmd.builder.charmm` module of HTMD, with the modified CHARMM36m [18] force field and the parameters for the modified mTIP3P [17] solvent model and the respective parameters for the ligand.

Each system was equilibrated using the `Equilibration_v2` module of HTMD [15]. It was first minimized using the conjugate-gradient method for 500 steps. Then, the system was heated to 310 K and minimized as follows: (i) 500 steps (2 ps) of NPT thermalization with the Berendsen barostat with $1 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{\AA}^{-2}$ constraints on all heavy atoms of the protein, (ii) 1250,000 steps (5 ns) of NVT equilibration with Langevin thermostat and the same constraints, and (iii) 1250,000 steps (5 ns) of NVT equilibration with the Langevin thermostat without any constraints. During the equilibration simulations, holonomic constraints were applied on all hydrogen-heavy atom bond terms and the mass of the hydrogen atoms was scaled with factor 4, enabling a 4 fs time step [19–22]. The simulations employed periodic boundary conditions, using the particle mesh Ewald method for the treatment of interactions beyond a 9 Å cut-off, and the smoothing and switching of van der Waals interaction was performed for a cut-off at 7.5 Å.

2.2. Adaptive sampling MDs to study dissociation

HTMD was used to perform adaptive sampling molecular dynamics simulations (MDs) to study the dissociation process of the ApoE dimers. For that, 50 ns production MD runs were started with the systems that resulted from the equilibration cycle and employed the same settings as the last step of the equilibration. The trajectories were saved every 0.1 ns. Adaptive sampling was performed using the root-mean square

deviation (RMSD) of the C α atoms with respect to the initial structure, and time-lagged independent component analysis (tICA) in 1 dimension [23]. Several epochs of 10 MDs each were performed for each system, until the dissociation of the dimers was observed or it reached a maximum of 20 epochs (corresponding to a cumulative time of 10 μ s).

2.3. Adaptive goal MDs to study self-association

We performed an adaptive sampling of the ApoE with the adaptive goal method implemented in HTMD to study the association process of the two chains into a dimer. For that, we identified, for each system, the individual MD from the previous adaptive sampling that displayed the most dissociated state of the dimer (showing the highest RMSD of the C α atoms). This MD was used as a starting point for the adaptive goal simulations.

For ApoE4 without SPA or TRN, the dissociation was not observed before 10 μ s. In this case, the two chains in the initial dimer were manually split, and with the HTMD scripts, they were randomly placed 15 Å apart from each other. The resulting system was solvated with a cubic box of TIP3P waters with the edges 22.5 Å from any atoms of the protein, and Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions were added to neutralize the system and achieve 0.1 M concentration of salt. This system was further parameterized and equilibrated as described above. This ensured a system of nearly the same size as for the previous adaptive sampling.

Adaptive goal simulations were performed with the goal function defined to minimize the RMSD of the C α atoms with respect to the initial crystal structure of the dimer (in a T-shape conformation). The exploration/exploitation ratio of the adaptive method (adg.ucscale parameter) was set to 0, to favor only the exploitation and disregard exploration. In doing so, we encouraged the systems to sample structures closer and closer to the T-shaped dimers. The MDs were run with the same settings as the last step of the equilibration described above. Overall, 19 or 20 epochs of 10 MDs each were performed for each system, corresponding to a cumulative time of ca. 10 μ s.

2.4. Post-processing of molecular dynamics simulations

The previous adaptive sampling and adaptive goal simulations were converted into a simulation list using HTMD [15], the water and ions were filtered out, the system was wrapped (to place all the molecules back into a single periodic simulation box), and unsuccessful MDs shorter than 50 ns were omitted. ParmEd was used to convert the CHARMM topologies to AMBER topologies [24]. The cpptraj [25] module of AmberTools 16 was used to concatenate the trajectories of each system, ordering the epochs chronologically, center and align them by their C α atoms, and save the combined trajectory in a single file for further analysis [12].

2.5. Interaction energies

The linear interaction energy (LIE) [26] was computed to assess the binding energy of each residue in the dimers of ApoE3 and ApoE4 with the SPA or TRN molecules, expressed as the respective electrostatic and van der Waals components, in the respective adaptive simulations. To this end, we used cpptraj to calculate the LIE on every snapshot of the combined MD trajectories. These interactions were calculated when the dimers were still associated, while we considered only the first 500 ns of the concatenated MD. This method was also used to assess the interaction energy between the two chains of the ApoE dimers in every system, with and without small molecules. These calculations were also performed on the first 500 ns of the concatenated adaptive simulations.

2.6. Dimensionality reduction and clustering analysis

The association adaptive goal simulations were analyzed by dimensionality reduction with the variational approach for Markov processes

(VAMP) (Wu and Noé, 2019), a technique suitable for detecting metastable states in off-equilibrium settings [27]. It is a method based on the Koopman theory, projecting the data onto the dominant components of the Koopman operator, which represent the slowest estimated processes. To ensure an unbiased exploration of all conformations formed during the simulation, all inter-chain inter-residue distances were used as input. A lag time of 15 ns was used. The data was projected onto the first 5 dominant VAMP dimensions. Frames with a minimum inter-heavy atom distance between the two ApoE chains exceeding 8 Å were filtered out and used to calculate the fraction of monomeric state in each system. After filtering, K-means clustering was applied to identify the metastable states.

2.7. Analysis of RMSD from reference structures

To further validate the results of VAMP clustering and provide a fair comparison between different systems, the RMSD to the reference structures of interest was computed for all frames across all ApoE3 and ApoE4 simulations (with and without TRN and SPA). The crystallographic T-shaped dimer, V-shaped dimer, parallel dimer, and the new conformation observed in our simulations, named anti-T-shaped dimer, were used as the reference structures. The reference structures of the T-shaped, V-shaped (previously described in [5]) and parallel dimers were obtained from the respective crystallographic structures by retrieving the symmetry mates with PyMOL, while the anti-T-shaped dimer reference structure was determined by selecting a frame from the respective cluster with strong LIE and visual assessment. The RMSD value was computed for both possible alignments of the two chains, i.e., A and B, taking the minimum value for each frame. The number of frames with RMSD to a given reference structure lower than the threshold of 6 Å was determined. This method allows obtaining a numerical value determining the proportion of frames close to the given reference structure for each system (even if the system lacked a VAMP cluster representing the given reference structure) and ensures that the discussed populations represent frames closely resembling reference structures.

2.8. Static light scattering (SLS)

SLS was recorded at 266 nm using an UNcle screening platform (UNChained Labs) at 37 °C. To this end, 10 μ M of commercially available full-length ApoE3 or ApoE4 (PeproTech) in 10 mM Tris 50 mM NaCl pH= 7.4 was mixed with 20 mM SPA, 20 mM TRN, or buffer (drug stock solutions were at 0.5 M in 1 M Tris pH=7.4) and then monitored for 14 h. Experiments were performed with three technical triplicates. Analytical fits were performed with KinTek (KinTek Corporation), with A_0 as a constant baseline, A_1 and $k_{obs,1}$ as amplitude and observed rate for the initial exponential phase, $k_{obs,2}$ as observed rate of follow-up linear drift:

$$y = A_0 + A_1 \cdot (1 - e^{k_{obs,1} \cdot t}) + k_{obs,2} \cdot t \quad (1)$$

We computed the change in aggregation as the drop in A_1 between ApoE4 alone ($A_1(\text{ApoE4})$) and in the presence of drug ($A_1(\text{drug})$) (Eq. 2):

$$\Delta = 1 - A_1(\text{drug}) / A_1(\text{ApoE4}) \quad (2)$$

T-test is performed using NORM.DIST function on Excel 2023 (Microsoft).

2.9. HDX-MS

Firstly, non-deuterated samples of full-length ApoE3 and ApoE4 proteins were prepared and analyzed separately using a mass spectrometer timsTOF SCP (Bruker) operated in data-dependent MS/MS mode with PASEF enabled. The identified peptides provided

information regarding their satisfactory number, sequence coverage, and redundancy. These optimized sample preparation and analysis conditions were then applied to HDX-MS analyses.

Control non-deuterated samples of ApoE3/4, both free and in complex with SPA or TRN, were diluted to a final concentration of 2 μM with a basic H_2O buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl, pH 7.5). A deuterated buffer of identical composition (pD 7.5, pH 7.1) was used for preparing deuterated samples. The Leap HDX robotic station (Trajan Scientific and Medical) was used to prepare each HDX time point by mixing 3 μl of protein, 3 μl of ligand in a 1:1000 molar ratio followed by pre-incubation at 2°C for 5 min and then dilution with 59 μl D_2O buffer making the final protein concentration to 2 μM , and the D_2O buffer composition was 90%. Four different time points, 60 s, 120 s, 600 s, and 1800 s, were quenched by adding a quenching buffer maintained at 2°C (6 M urea in 1 M glycine, pH 2.3) in a 1:1 ratio. All samples were prepared in triplicates.

100 pmoles of each quenched sample were directly injected into an immobilized dual pepsin column (Pepsin/Nepenthesin2, AffiPro) at a flow rate of 200 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ with the loading buffer (0.1% formic acid). Peptides were trapped and desalted on-line on a peptide microtrap (Phenomenex UHPLC Fully porous polar C18, 2.1 mm) for 3 min before elution onto an analytical column (Phenomenex Luna Omega Polar C18 analytical column 1.6 μm , 100 \times 1.0 mm, 100 Å), maintained at 2°C. A 6-min linear-gradient (10%-45%) with 80% acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid was used to separate the peptides (Agilent 1290). The eluate from the analytical column was directed into the timsTOF SCP mass spectrometer (Bruker) with electrospray ionization. Blank injections were performed between each sample injection to prevent the carryover of peptides between runs. HDX samples were analyzed in MS mode without trapped ion mobility.

Tandem mass spectra were searched using MASCOT against the cRAP and contaminants protein database (http://ftp.thegpm.org/fast_a/cRAP), containing the sequences of ApoE3 and ApoE4, with precursor ion mass tolerance set at 10 ppm and fragment ion mass tolerance at 0.05 Da. No enzyme specificity was applied, with a maximum allowance of two missed cleavages, and no fixed or variable modifications. The false discovery rate at the peptide identification level was set to 1%. The peptide map was prepared using the DigDig software, version 0.8.1 [28] and peptide redundancy was calculated. The MS raw files of deuterated and non-deuterated samples, along with the list of peptides and their parameters (score, retention time, charge, sequence, and mobility), were analyzed using HDExaminer version 3.4.1 (Sierra Analytics, Modesto, CA) [29]. The software analyzed peptide-level deuteration over time and calculated the score based on the fit of theoretical and actual isotope clusters. Confidence levels were assigned as high, medium, or low. Peptides were manually reviewed to improve the fit, and only high- and medium-confidence peptides, up to 20 amino acids in length, were included in further calculations.

PyHDX v0.4.3 [30] was then used to calculate relative fractional uptake (RFU), a normalized measurement used in HDX-MS to quantify the amount of deuterium exchanged by a protein's backbone amides relative to its maximum potential capacity, allowing comparison of D-uptake across all states. RFU serves as a proxy for protein dynamics and solvent accessibility. High RFU values (closer to 1 or 100%) indicate regions that are highly dynamic, disordered, or highly exposed to the solvent, as they exchange hydrogen for deuterium rapidly. Low RFU values indicate "rigid" or protected regions, such as those buried in the protein core or involved in stable secondary structures (like α -helices), where hydrogen bonding prevents exchange. Relative Fractional Uptake (often expressed as the corrected D-uptake, $D_{\text{corr}}(t)$) is used to standardize measurements by comparing the observed exchange to a fully deuterated control (Eq. 3).

$$D_{\text{corr}}(t) = D(t)/D(\text{FD}) \cdot n_{\text{labile}} \quad (3)$$

$D(t)$ is the experimentally measured D-uptake at a specific exposure time (t); $D(\text{FD})$ is the D-uptake of the fully deuterated control sample

(theoretical), which represents the maximal degree of deuterium exchange possible for that specific peptide; n_{labile} stands for the number of exchange-competent amide groups in the peptide. This is typically calculated as the total number of residues in the peptide minus the number of proline residues and minus the first (or first two) N-terminal residues, as these do not retain deuterium due to high intrinsic exchange rates. RFU values for free ApoE3/4 and ligand-bound forms were calculated by weighted averaging, where each residue's RFU was determined by averaging RFUs of overlapping peptides, weighted by the inverse peptide length, and visualized in a linear bar plot [31,32].

To compare two states, Differential RFU (ΔRFU), a value obtained by subtracting the RFU of one state (e.g., a "free" protein) from another (e.g., a "ligand-bound" protein) was calculated (Eq. 4).

$$\Delta\text{RFU} = \text{RFU}_{\text{ligand-bound state}} - \text{RFU}_{\text{free state}} \quad (4)$$

Positive ΔRFU denotes higher D-uptake upon ligand binding, while negative ΔRFU indicates lower D-uptake. All RFU and ΔRFU values are provided in the [supplementary dataset \(Table S5\)](#).

2.10. Binding interaction measurements

Tryptophan fluorescence measurements were performed using a Fluoromax Plus spectrofluorometer (Horiba, Japan). Emission spectra were recorded at 37 °C in 1 M Tris, pH 8.0 upon excitation at 280 nm, with both excitation and emission slit widths set to 5 nm. The emission spectra were collected from 300 to 450 nm. The photomultiplier tube (PMT) voltage was set to 700 V, and the integration time for each data point was 0.1 s. ApoE was used at a final concentration of 30 μM and titrated with increasing concentrations of the tested compounds: 10 μM , 100 μM , 1 mM, 2 mM, 5 mM, 10 mM, 20 mM, and 30 mM. The final DMSO concentration was maintained at 5% (v/v) in all samples. Each binding experiment was measured in triplicate.

2.11. Binding data analysis and statistics

Concentration-dependent tryptophan fluorescence spectra of ApoE titrated with selected ligands were analyzed by singular value decomposition (SVD) to reduce experimental noise and identify the dominant spectral components corresponding to the protein–ligand interaction. SVD identified two significant eigenvalue–eigenvector pairs, corresponding to the spectral contributions of free ApoE and the ApoE–ligand complex. The amplitude vectors, scaled by their singular values to account for relative significance, were globally fit to an approximate binding model $E + L \rightleftharpoons E.L$, where E is ApoE, L is the ligand, and E.L is the complex, using KinTek Explorer software (KinTek Corporation, USA) [33]. Fitting was performed by nonlinear regression based on numerical integration of the rate equations; the resulting equilibrium dissociation constants ($K_{\text{D,app}}$) are interpreted as apparent binding parameters, as the 1:1 model serves as an approximation of the more complex binding behavior of ApoE–ligand interactions. Parameter optimization employed the Bulirsch–Stoer algorithm with adaptive step size to minimize χ^2 , calculated by the Levenberg–Marquardt method. Residuals were normalized by the sigma value of each data point. Standard errors (s.e.) were derived from the covariance matrix of the nonlinear regression, and parameter robustness was further evaluated by confidence contour analysis [34], with upper and lower bounds determined from χ^2 thresholds at the 0.95 confidence level.

2.12. Aggregate dissociation assay

ApoE3 and ApoE4 samples (30 μM each) were incubated at 37 °C in 1 M Tris, pH 8.0, for 4 h to allow aggregate formation. Subsequently, TRN, TMP and SPA were added to a final concentration of 30 mM. The dissociation of aggregates was monitored by static light scattering (SLS) at 37 °C for 20 h using a Prometheus Panta instrument (NanoTemper Technologies, Germany). Each condition was measured in triplicate, and

the data were averaged. Aggregated ApoE3 and ApoE4 samples without added compounds served as controls.

2.13. Stem cell culture

Two isogenic human iPSC lines used in this study were passaged and maintained using standard feeder-free culture protocols. In brief, feeder-free cultures were grown on Matrigel-coated plates (Corning) in mTeSRTM1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies) supplemented with half of the recommended dose of ZellShield® (Minerva Biolabs). Cells were passaged using 0.5 mM EDTA (Thermo Fisher Scientific) in PBS or manually. The “E4” cell line was derived from a patient with a sporadic form of AD with ApoE4/4 status. The isogenic cell line “E3” was obtained by correction of ApoE4/4 to ApoE3/3. Both isogenic iPSC lines were kindly provided by Dr. Li-Huei Tsai and described previously [35].

2.14. CO culture and TRN treatment

COs were generated using the protocol described previously, where the cellular composition of our organoids was characterized by single-cell sequencing [36,37]. Briefly, for spheroid formation, cells were plated at day 0 into non-adherent V-shaped 96-well plates at 2000–3000 cells in 150 μ l of mTeSRTM1 medium with 50 μ M ROCK inhibitor (S1049, Selleckchem). Plates were centrifuged for 2 min at 200 g to facilitate spheroid formation. Non-adherent cell culture plates were prepared with poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (poly-HEMA; P3932, Merck) coating. On day 2, the cell culture medium was exchanged for fresh mTeSRTM1 without ROCK inhibitor. When spheroids reached the size of 400–600 μ m, fresh Neural Induction Medium was added every day for six days (usually from day 3 to day 8) [38]. The next day, twelve organoids were transferred to one 6 cm cell culture dish. The remaining medium was aspirated, and dry organoids were embedded in 7 μ l of cold GeltrexTM (Thermo Fisher). GeltrexTM was left to solidify as hanging drops on the inverted cell culture dish for 10 min at 37 °C. Solidified GeltrexTM drops with organoids were gently detached from the bottom and cultured without shaking in Cerebral Organoid Differentiation Medium (CODM) [38] without vitamin A for seven days. Subsequently, organoids were cultured in CODM with vitamin A and were moved on an orbital shaker on day 26 (\pm two days). CODM was changed three times a week by aspirating at least half of the old medium and replacing it with a fresh medium. ZellShield® (Minerva Biolabs) was used to prevent contamination in all media. The treatment with TRN or TMP was performed for 50 days, from day 50 (D50) to day 100 (D100). During this period, CODM was continuously supplemented with 100 μ M TRN or 100 μ M TMP, both prepared directly in cell culture medium without the use of any additional solvent or vehicle. Samples were harvested from three independent CO differentiation cultures, each performed on a different experimental day. Control samples (NTR) were treated with medium only.

2.15. Cryo-sections, immunohistochemistry (IHC) and microscopic analysis

Harvested COs were fixed with 3.7% paraformaldehyde for 1 h and washed with PBS. For cryo-sections, fixed organoids were saturated with 30% sucrose (Merck), embedded in O.C.T. medium (Tissue-Tek), and frozen. Then, 10 μ m sections were prepared on cryostat Leica 1850. Excess O.C.T. medium was removed by 15 min PBS wash prior to IHC staining. Sections were permeabilized in 0.2% Triton-X (Merck) in PBS and blocked in 2% normal goat serum (Merck) in permeabilization solution. Samples were incubated with primary antibodies in a blocking solution at 4 °C overnight followed by incubation with secondary antibodies (Alexa FluorTM; Thermo Fischer Scientific) for 1 h at room temperature. Nuclei were visualized by Hoechst 33342 (Thermo Fischer Scientific). The following primary antibodies were used:

MAP2 (#8707; CST), DCX (sc-271390; Santa Cruz Biotechnology),

TUJ (#4466; CST), and S100 β (ab11178; Abcam). Samples were imaged with the inverted microscope Zeiss Axio Observer.Z1 with confocal unit LSM 800.

2.16. Sample preparation for proteomic assays

For proteomic assays, individual organoids were washed with PBS on D100, incubated in Cell Recovery Solution (Corning) for 1 h, washed with PBS, and stored at -80 °C. Five to six organoids from three independent CO differentiation batches were harvested for analysis (in total 15–16 organoids were used for analysis per condition). Each batch was initiated on a different day.

2.17. RNA isolation and mRNA sequencing

Harvested organoids were washed with PBS, lysed with 1 ml RNA Blue reagent (Top-Bio), and stored at -80 °C. Total RNA was isolated from three biological replicates (ApoE3/3 =E3; ApoE4/4 =E4) for each condition (NTR, TMP, TRN) with Direct-zol RNA Microprep kit (ZymoResearch) according to the manufacturer’s instructions. Biological replicates represent independent organoid differentiations derived from separate cultures performed on different experimental days. Each biological replicate consisted of a pool of 5–6 organoids. RNA quality was assessed by TapeStation 2200 (Agilent Technologies; RNA Screen Tape), and only samples with RINe values \geq 8.5 were used for library preparation. Poly-A selected libraries were made from 300 ng of total RNA using QuantSeq FWD 3’ mRNA Library Prep Kit (Lexogen) in combination with UMI Second Strand Synthesis Module for QuantSeq FWD and Lexogen i5 6 nt Unique Dual Indexing Add-on Kit (Lexogen) with 14, 18x PCR cycles according to the manufacturer’s instructions. Quality control of library quantity and size distribution was done using QuantiFluor dsDNA System (Promega) and High Sensitivity NGS Fragment Analysis Kit (Agilent Technologies). The final library pool was sequenced on NextSeq 500 (Illumina) using High Output Kit v2.5 75 Cycles in single-end mode, resulting in an average of 10 million reads per sample.

2.18. Alignment of RNA-seq samples and quality control

The raw reads were initially trimmed using Trimmomatic [39] and subsequently mapped to the human reference genome hg38 with STAR (v.2.7.3) [40]. Transcript-level expression quantification was carried out using RSEM [40], with results aggregated at the gene level according to GENCODE (v.30) [41]. RNA-SeqQC [42] and Picard (v2.2.4) tools were employed to assess the quality control metrics, which included the number of aligned reads (minimum average of 8.740 ± 0.593 million), the fractions of duplicate reads (0.723 ± 0.057), the fractions of uniquely mapped reads (0.75 ± 0.020), and the mean GC content ($40.597\% \pm 0.630\%$). No systematic differences were observed among the replicates or across the samples.

2.19. Differential gene expression analysis

To identify genes that showed differential expression between treatments (NTR/TRN/TMP), a differential gene expression (DGE) analysis was performed. A joint count matrix was generated across all samples, and genes with low expression were filtered by retaining only those with counts per million (CPM) \geq 4 in at least 15% of samples. Expression values were modeled using the dream function from the variancePartition package (v1.0.27) [43,44], which fits linear mixed models. The model included fixed effects for treatment (NTR, TMP, TRN), genotype (ApoE3/3 vs ApoE4/4), and their interaction. Biological replicate was included as a random effect to account for repeated measures structure. Technical confounders were controlled by including sequencing batch and the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) derived from a set of sample-level quality metrics. Given the modest

sample size, QC covariates were summarized using principal component analysis to reduce dimensionality and mitigate overfitting, while retaining the dominant sources of technical variation. These metrics included proportions of intronic, intergenic, coding, ribosomal, and mRNA reads, GC content, fractions of uniquely mapped, duplicate, chimeric, and too-short reads, as well as estimated cell-type proportions (GABAergic neurons, glutamatergic neurons, astrocytes, and oligodendrocytes). Differential expression was assessed using moderated t-statistics, and resulting p-values were adjusted for multiple testing using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure. Contrasts were extracted to compare treatment effects within and across genotypes.

2.20. Visualisation and further analysis of mRNA sequencing data

For downstream analyses, genes showing at least minimal expression and differential regulation in any contrast (adjusted p-value < 0.1 and $|\log_2 \text{fold change}| > 0.6$ in at least one comparison) were selected to define a gene set of interest ($n = 206$). This selection was used for exploratory visualization and hypothesis-generating analyses and does not represent an independent statistical testing step. Functional enrichment analysis of this gene set was performed using g:Profiler [45] (g:Profiler version e111_eg58_p18_b51d8f08) as described previously [46]. To further explore expression patterns across conditions, selected genes were visualized across ApoE3 and ApoE4 backgrounds (E3_NTR, E4_NTR, E4_TRN, E4_TMP). Differences in expression distributions were assessed using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests in GraphPad Prism v8. These analyses were performed for exploratory comparison of expression patterns across conditions and were not used for primary inference of differential expression, which was based on the full dataset using the statistical model described above.

2.21. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry protein analysis (LC-MS/MS)

CO tissue samples were processed using the protocol and analyzed using the LC-MS/MS assay (including data processing) as described previously [5]. The following reagents were used: LC/MS grade Acetonitrile (ACN, 34967), Isopropanol (IPA, 34965), and Formic acid (FA) were obtained from Honeywell (Charlotte, USA), Ammonium bicarbonate (AmBic, BioUltra, $\geq 99.5\%$ purity, 09830), Sodium deoxycholate (SDC, BioXtra, $\geq 98.0\%$ purity, 30970), Iodoacetamide (IAA, $\geq 99\%$ purity, I6125) from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), 1,4-dithiothreitol (DTT, $\geq 99\%$ purity, 6908.1) from Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG (Karlsruhe, Germany), Trypsin gold, Mass Spec Grade, from Promega (Madison, WI, USA), Pierce BCA Protein Assay Kit reagents from ThermoFisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Synthetic isotopically labeled (SIL) peptide standards (SpikeTides_L crude) were synthesized by JPT Peptide Technologies Inc. (Acton, MA, USA). The ultrapure water was prepared using the water purification system (arium® Comfort System, Sartorius).

COs (stored at -80°C) were lyophilized using SpeedVac vacuum concentrator (Savant SDP121 P, ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) and homogenized with glass bead (BeadBlaster™ 24, Benchmark Scientific, Edison, NJ, USA). Proteins were precipitated with 80% IPA (100 μl). Protein pellets formed after vortexing (VELP Scientifica), sonication (37 Hz, 5 min; Elmasonic P, Elma Schmidbauer GmbH) and mixing (200 rpm, 10 min; Heidolph™ MultiReax) was centrifuged (12.3 RCF, 5 min; Micro-Star 12, VWR®, Radnor, PA, USA) and dried in SpeedVac after removal of the supernatant. The dried protein pellets were solubilized by adding 100 μl AmBic buffer (100 mM) with SDC (5 mg/ml) (AmBic+SDC). All samples were vortexed (10 s, 2000 rpm), homogenized (4 m/s, 10 s, two cycles with 10 s inter-time), sonicated (1 min, 80 kHz, Elmasonic P, Elma Schmidbauer GmbH), mixed (10 min, 2035 rpm) and centrifuged (1 min, 12,300 RCF). The total protein content ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in each protein homogenate sample was measured using the BCA protein assay. The protein concentration in each sample was

adjusted to 0.1–0.3 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ by adding the AmBic+SDC buffer. After centrifugation, aliquots of 60 μl (6–18 μg of total protein) were reduced with 20 mM DTT in 50 mM AmBic (10 min; 95°C) and alkylated with 40 mM IAA in 50 mM AmBic (30 min; room temperature in the dark). The remaining homogenates from individual COs were mixed to prepare a quality control (QC) sample for calibration curve measurements. The samples were digested with trypsin (1:20–40, enzyme: total protein, w/w), sealed and incubated (37°C ; 16 h) with gentle shaking. The digestion was stopped by acidification with 2% FA (200 μl), and SIL peptide standards were added to the samples in a final concentration of ≈ 22 –29 nmol/l. Peptide mixtures were then purified using the solid-phase extraction (SPE) method (mixed-mode cartridge, Oasis® PRiME HLB – 30 mg, Waters Corp. Milford, MA, USA): after loading on the column sorbent, the samples were washed with 2% FA, eluted with 500 μl of 50% ACN with 2% FA and dried in SpeedVac.

The samples were reconstituted in 5% ACN with 0.1% FA (15–20 μl). Analysis of peptides was performed on the LC-MS/MS system (UHPLC Agilent 1290 Infinity II coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer Agilent 6495B, Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) operated in a positive ion detection mode. Samples (3 μl) were injected into the C18 analytical column (Acquity UPLC CSH 1.7 μm , 2.1 mm \times 100 mm, Waters Corporation, MA, USA). The gradient mode of mobile phases A (0.1% FA) and B (0.1% FA in 95% ACN) was: initial 5% B; 25 min 30% B; 25.5 min 95% B; 30 min 95% B; and from 31 to 35 min with 5% B; flow rate was set to 0.3 ml/min. The electrospray ionization (ESI) source parameters were: temperature = 200°C , capillary voltage = 3500 V. The same multiplex selected reaction monitoring (SRM) assay was used for the detection and relative quantification of protein targets in the COs as published in the previous study [5]. Manually inspected data were processed in Skyline software (version 21.2.0.369, MacCoss Lab, UW, USA). Peptide transitions with a reproducible signal (on average, % CV < 15%) selected for the relative quantification of proteins shown in the study are listed in Table S1. Calculated protein concentrations using the peak area of the spiked SIL peptide standards were normalized to the GAPDH levels. The final results were visualized as fold-change values in this study, i.e. analyzed protein levels in TRN-treated E3 and E4 organoids (E3_TRN, E4_TRN) were related to the corresponding non-treated (NTR) E3 and E4 organoids (E3_NTR, E4_NTR) in each batch to see the effect of TRN protein expression relative to protein levels found in organoids without the treatment. Thus, NTR values are displayed as 1 for each genotype and are not intended for direct comparison between ApoE3 and ApoE4, but rather to show the effect of TRN treatment within each genotype.

3. Results

3.1. TRN promotes ApoE4 T-shaped dimer dissociation through electrostatic interactions

To assess the TRN-ApoE4 interaction, we simulated the dissociation of ApoE dimers, using adaptive sampling molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, starting from a T-shaped dimeric state of ApoE3 and ApoE4 (Fig. 2A), alone or in the presence of 100 small molecules (TRN or SPA).

We measured the evolution of the root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) of the protein $\text{C}\alpha$ atoms with respect to their starting structures, setting the threshold for tracking the dimer dissociation to RMSD values above 15 Å. Most systems (ApoE4 with SPA or TRN, free ApoE3) showed dissociation after ca. 1.5 – 3 μs of combined simulation times (Fig. 2A), while the free ApoE4 took one order of magnitude longer to dissociate (16 μs). These results suggest that both TRN and SPA can exert a similar effect in promoting the dissociation of ApoE4 T-shaped dimers.

The interface interactions in the ApoE T-shaped dimers, as assessed by the linear interaction energies, LIE [26,47] during the initial part of the adaptive simulations (first 500 ns), are mainly driven by electrostatic interactions, which were nearly one order of magnitude stronger than the van der Waals component (Fig. 2B). These energies were

Fig. 2. TRN and SPA bind to the N-terminal (residues 22–165) of ApoE T-shaped dimers and promote their dissociation. (A) RMSD of Ca atoms during the dissociation adaptive MD simulations of ApoE3 (left) and ApoE4 (right) T-shaped dimers, alone (black) or in the presence of TRN (purple) or SPA (pink). (B) Electrostatic (E_{elec}) and van der Waals (E_{vdw}) components of the linear interaction energy (LIE, in kcal/mol) between the two protomer chains of ApoE3 and ApoE4 T-shaped dimers, alone or in the presence of SPA or TRN molecules, during the adaptive MDs; the uncertainty values represent the standard deviation of the mean energies in the initial 500 ns (5000 snapshots). (C) Electrostatic component (E_{elec}) of LIE between TRN or SPA with every residue of each chain (A and B, as defined in Fig. 1B) of ApoE₄ T-shaped dimer, during the adaptive MDs; the uncertainty bars represent the standard deviation of the mean energies during the initial 500 ns (5000 snapshots). Colored boxes highlight regions where TRN and SPA preferentially bind. See Fig. S2 for data with ApoE3.

stronger for ApoE4 than for ApoE3, which agrees with the observation that the dimer dissociation was much slower for ApoE4 than for ApoE3. The presence of TRN or SPA significantly decreased the electrostatic interactions between the two protomers (for ApoE4, by ca. 82 kcal/mol and 73 kcal/mol, respectively), which may explain the higher dissociation propensity of the dimers in the presence of those small molecules. To understand the effects of TRN and SPA at the molecular level, we assessed the binding energies of those small molecules to the amino acids of dimeric ApoE3 and ApoE4, during the same simulations. The van der Waals component of LIE was negligible compared to the electrostatic one. The results also revealed that TRN binds to the same regions of the dimers as SPA but with weaker interaction energies (Fig. 2C and S1). Most of the dimer-interface residues in chain A are positively charged, while those in chain B are negatively charged. Total interaction energies were stronger with SPA (more negative) than with TRN, although TRN interacted with more residues than SPA. This is because TRN has one positive and one negative moiety, while SPA has two negative moieties. The variability of interaction energies is large for both TRN and SPA due to the nonspecific nature of those interactions, which results in a relatively fast on/off switch of the contacts between the ligands and the residues. The strong electrostatic interactions of TRN and SPA with the charged dimer-interface residues interfered with the protein-protein interactions in that region (Fig. 2C), weakening them and ultimately contributing to their faster dissociation. These effects have previously been observed for SPA [5].

The receptor-binding domain in ApoE consists of the arginine-rich

region of residues 136–150, on helix H4 [48]. We analyzed the MD simulations of dimeric ApoE3 and ApoE4 in the presence of 100 molecules SPA and TRN. By computing the occupancy of these molecules around the proteins, we identified regions with higher molecular density (Figure S1). We observed that the regions with the highest occupancy for both SPA and TRN correspond to the receptor-binding domain and neighboring areas. In the case of SPA, the highest density is located directly above the receptor-binding residues. For TRN, the densest region is partially overlapping the receptor-binding site, but is also shifted toward helices H3 and H4, which contain both negatively and positively charged residues. This difference likely arises from the distinct charge properties of the two molecules, with SPA being doubly negative, while TRN is zwitterionic. This agrees with the interaction energies represented in Fig. 2C. Comparing ApoE3 and ApoE4 (Figure S2), we did not observe many significant differences, except that both SPA and TRN showed an increased density around the mutated residue R112 in ApoE4.

Based on these observations, both SPA and TRN are predicted to weaken receptor interactions with the two ApoE isoforms through electrostatic competition with charged residues at the receptor-binding site. This effect is similar to the disruptions induced by the same molecules on the electrostatic-dominated dimer interfaces, which are described above. Moreover, SPA is expected to exert a stronger effect than TRN because (1) its double negative charge causes stronger electrostatic repulsion with negatively charged residues in the receptor, compared to the zwitterionic TRN, and (2) due to its more direct and

extensive interaction with the receptor-binding region of ApoE.

We tested the effect of SPA and TRN on ApoE dimer association with adaptive goal MD simulations. Monomeric states were defined as those in which the minimum distance between heavy atoms of different chains is at least 8 Å. The proportion of monomeric states increased by a factor of approximately two in the presence of either SPA or TRN, indicating that both molecules can reduce non-specific ApoE-ApoE interactions (Fig. 3A). This observation was robust to the selection of the distance threshold (Figure S3). Although the overall number of non-specific ApoE-ApoE interactions in the ApoE4 system is slightly higher, it remains comparable to that in the ApoE3 systems, both in the presence and absence of the compounds. To better understand the experimentally observed higher aggregation propensity of ApoE4, we analyzed dimer formation using VAMP, revealing several different ApoE dimeric conformations, including parallel, V-shaped, T-shaped, and anti-T-shaped dimers (Fig. 3B-C, Table S2, Figure S4). This analysis allowed us to identify distinct structural states that may contribute to the higher aggregation propensity of ApoE4.

We present the VAMP clustering results only for the most aggregation-prone system, i.e. free ApoE4, which we used to determine the conformations of interest. To the best of our knowledge, only the T-shaped, V-shaped and parallel dimers have been observed in crystallographic structures [5]. Previously, we experimentally identified T- and V-shaped dimers as protein-protein crystallographic dimers, then later confirmed as native protein dimers by mutagenesis. The difference between these two dimers lies in the angle between the two chains. Likewise, parallel crystallographic dimers were also observed in the simulations but have not been validated experimentally.

The VAMP analysis identified the parallel dimer as forming the largest cluster observed in the free ApoE4 system, consisting of 11.5% of all frames in the adaptive goal simulation (Fig. 3A-B). The RMSD analysis confirmed that 7.6% of the free ApoE4 frames had RMSD values below 6 Å when compared to the crystallographic parallel dimer. This percentage decreased to 1.7% in the presence of TRN and dropped to 0.0% with SPA, suggesting a higher efficacy of SPA at preventing parallel dimer formation. Both SPA and TRN formed favorable interactions with helix H4 (Fig. 2C), which is also a critical component of the parallel dimer interface (Figure S5). Interestingly, only small or inexistent populations of parallel dimers were observed in the ApoE3 systems (0.5% for free ApoE3, 0.0% for ApoE3 with TRN, and 0.1% for ApoE3 with SPA) (Table S2). We observed the formation of a new and unique dimer,

which we termed "anti-T-shaped dimer" in reference to the T-shaped dimer previously described [5], since chain B interacts with the opposite side of chain A (Fig. 3B). A key observation is that the mutated residue at position 112 (C112 for ApoE3, R112 for ApoE4) appears to be involved in the interface of this dimer. Notably, the anti-T-shaped VAMP cluster was detected only in the free ApoE4 system (Fig. 3B), and the RMSD analysis confirmed that these interactions were unique to this system (Table S2). While interactions involving the mutated residue at position 112 could be of particular interest, potentially offering direct insights into the mutational effects from ApoE3 to ApoE4, this anti-T-shaped dimer has never been observed experimentally thus far.

Altogether, our simulations demonstrated that SPA and TRN effectively increase the population of monomeric species, indicating their ability to prevent ApoE dimer association. VAMP clustering revealed diverse ApoE dimer conformations, with the fractions of the parallel dimer of ApoE4 being significantly reduced in the presence of SPA and TRN. Both molecules interact favorably with helix H4, crucial for parallel dimer formation. Additionally, a unique anti-T-shaped dimer was identified in the ApoE4 system, involving the mutated residue at position 112, although this finding remains to be validated experimentally.

3.2. TRN suppresses ApoE4 aggregation and modifies its dynamics

While molecular dynamics provides insights into the initial stages of the ApoE aggregation, the simulation of the entire aggregation process involving dozens or possibly hundreds of protomers is computationally too demanding. Therefore, we utilized static light scattering (SLS) to experimentally monitor protein aggregation in real-time.

Full-length ApoE3 or ApoE4 (10 μM) was mixed with a 2000-fold excess of SPA, a metabolite of the prodrug TMP [5], or with TRN. This concentration was selected based on previous *in vitro* studies and clinically relevant dosages carried out with these small molecules [52]. As expected, ApoE3 showed minimal aggregation, whereas ApoE4 aggregated rapidly. TRN and SPA both significantly suppressed ApoE4 aggregation (Fig. 4A). To quantify the extent of ApoE aggregation inhibition, we fitted the aggregation curves analytically with a single exponential function with a linear drift component (Fig. 4B, Table S3). The amplitude of the initial exponential aggregation phase (A_1), which describes the amount of aggregated ApoE in the initial exponential aggregation phase, was significantly reduced in the presence of SPA ($\Delta = 73 \pm 10\%$ less aggregation) or TRN ($\Delta = 40 \pm 7\%$ less aggregation), as

Fig. 3. VAMP classification of ApoE dimers and inhibition by TRN and SPA. (A) Percentage of monomeric states in all systems. (B) Representative frames and dimer type for each VAMP cluster of free ApoE4 (as described in (C)). (C) Free energy landscape (grey shades) and VAMP clusters (represented by the coloured ellipses) of the dimeric states of free ApoE4 during the association adaptive goal MDs. Structures are colored as described in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4. TRN and SPA suppress ApoE4 aggregation and solvation. (A) Static light scattering (SLS) of ApoE3 (grey), free ApoE4 (black) and ApoE4 with a 2000-fold excess of SPA (pink) or TRN (purple). The data was collected in 10 mM Tris 50 mM NaCl pH = 7.4 buffer at 37°C. (B) Fitted amplitudes of the initial aggregation phase (A_1) using a single exponential function with linear drift component (Eq. 1). All fitted parameters are given in Table S1. Error bars represent standard errors. ***: p-value < 0.0001 for T-test.

compared to ApoE4 alone (p-values < 0.0001). This result confirms that both compounds can decrease ApoE4 aggregation, with SPA having a stronger inhibitory effect.

3.3. Binding experiments reveal weak, multivalent binding of TRN to ApoE

Intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence was used to characterize ligand binding to ApoE without external labeling or immobilization. ApoE4 showed larger signal deviations than ApoE3, reflecting its lower stability and higher aggregation propensity, which complicates maintaining a defined protein concentration during titrations (Figure S6). To account for ApoE4 instability during fluorescence titrations, all binding experiments were performed in triplicate; raw replicate variability and confidence contours of the fitted parameters are provided in Figure S7. Simple spectral analyses based on intensity, 350/330 ratio, or average emission wavelength (AEW) were insufficient. Multidimensional singular value decomposition (SVD) captured full spectral information, including intensity changes, peak shifts, and spectral shape variations from multiple Trp residues of ApoE. SVD reduced experimental noise and enabled the extraction of dominant spectral components associated with ApoE–ligand interactions (Figure S7). The resulting data indicate that TRN, TMP, and SPA bind ApoE weakly, with $K_{D,app}$ values in the millimolar range (Table S4) and protein:ligand ratios approaching ~1:100. These interactions are consistent with a non-stoichiometric, multivalent binding mode rather than a single high-affinity 1:1 interaction.

3.4. TRN dissociates pre-formed aggregates

Static light scattering (SLS) was used to monitor aggregate dissociation (Figure S8). Upon addition of TRN, TMP and SPA, pre-aggregated ApoE4 exhibited a fast decrease in SLS signal, likely reflecting partial dissociation or reduction in aggregate size. A similar decrease was observed in controls without small molecules, indicating the effect of sample dilution. The addition of TRN or SPA caused a more pronounced reduction in aggregates than mere dilution, and SPA had the strongest effect: upon addition of SPA, the signal decreased almost instantaneously within the dead time of the experiment (the period between mixing and the start of signal acquisition), and only a low SLS signal level was observed, indicating the absence of aggregates. After ~3–5 h, the SLS signal increased, indicative of secondary aggregation, which was substantially mitigated by TRN and completely prevented by SPA

(Figure S8). In contrast, ApoE3 displayed minimal aggregation during pre-incubation and slow, gradual aggregation over 24 h. All three tested ligands reduced ApoE3 aggregation, with SPA showing the strongest effect.

3.5. TRN modifies ApoE stability

To measure and compare ligand-dependent changes in lipid-free ApoE backbone deuterium uptake kinetics, we performed bottom-up HDX-MS on full-length, WT ApoE3 and ApoE4 in the absence and presence of TRN or SPA. Non-deuterated controls provided 100% sequence coverage; after filtering identifications to retain only distinct peptide species meeting our quality criteria, we obtained 840 and 857 unique peptides for ApoE3 and ApoE4, respectively. The peptide coverage map and sequence redundancy are shown in Figures S9–S11. At the 60 s exchange time, Fig. 5A and Figure S12 further summarizes the RFU profiles of ligand-free ApoE3 and ApoE4 and the ligand-induced response of ApoE4 to SPA and TRN, aligned to the annotated secondary-structure elements. In the ligand-free comparison, ApoE4 shows slightly higher RFU than ApoE3 in N1 and H1 and in parts of H2 and H3, whereas lower RFU is apparent in H4 and C1, indicating region-dependent differences in backbone protection between the isoforms at early exchange. Upon addition of SPA or TRN, ApoE4 exhibits a distributed decrease in RFU across multiple N-terminal domain (NTD, H2–H4), extending into hinge-domain (HD) and C-terminal domain (CTD); the corresponding residue-resolved Δ RFU mapping in Fig. 5B–D and Figure S13 confirms that these effects are spatially widespread rather than confined to a single site. All the datasets are included in the supplementary dataset (Table S5).

This time-resolved behavior is reinforced by the peptide-level and residue-level uptake kinetics in Figure S14–15, where representative peptides from the NTD region (e.g., 7–18, 72–79, 98–104, 106–116, 109–116, 127–137) and from the hinge/CTD region (e.g., 216–234 and 257–271) show consistently lower deuterium uptake for ApoE4 + TRN or ApoE4 + SPA than for ApoE4 free at each time point, demonstrating that the protection is already apparent at early exchange and persists through late labeling times.

3.6. TRN modifies the expression profile of ApoE4/E4 organoids

To explore the effect of TRN on a human-relevant cellular model, we used induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived COs differentiated from an isogenic pair of cell lines carrying ApoE3/E3 or ApoE4/E4

Fig. 5. HDX-MS of ApoE4 with TRN. (A) Relative fractional uptake (RFU) over amino acid residues for ApoE3, ApoE4, ApoE4 + SPA, and ApoE4 + TRN after 60 s of deuterium exposure represented in grey, black, pink, and purple, respectively (see legend). Data were collected at four-time intervals: 60 s, 120 s, 600 s, and 1800 s (B) ΔRFU values of ApoE4 ($\Delta\text{RFU}_{\text{ApoE4 Free}}$, $\Delta\text{RFU}_{\text{ApoE3 Free}}$) (C) ApoE4 + TRN ($\Delta\text{RFU}_{\text{Apo4+TRN}}$, $\Delta\text{RFU}_{\text{ApoE4 Free}}$), mapped on the structure of ApoE (PDB 2L7B), showing regions of differential RFU. (D) ΔRFU heatmap mapped on the amino acid sequences of ApoE4. Differences are highlighted in red and blue. Red regions ($\Delta\text{RFU} > 0$) indicate suggest increased amide hydrogen to deuterium exchange compared to the free protein, while blue regions ($\Delta\text{RFU} < 0$) indicate reduced exchange. The mutation site (C112R) is highlighted in red with an asterisk. Proline residues, non-exchangeable in HDX-MS, are indicated in grey.

genotype [35]. As schematized in Fig. 6A, both cell lines were used to generate mature COs with an organized morphology and expressing standard neuronal and glial markers, i.e., DCX, TUJ, MAP2, and S100b, respectively (Fig. 6B). At day 50 of *in vitro* culture, 100 μM TRN or TMP, a precursor of SPA [5], was added to the cell culture media of both ApoE3/E3 and ApoE4/E4 organoids and maintained in the organoid culture media for another 50 days, with media exchange every 2–3 days. On day 100 of *in vitro* culture, organoids were harvested for transcriptomic and proteomic analyses. All experiments were performed in three independent batches, and data were processed as described in the methods.

Interestingly, our data analysis revealed that TRN treatment specifically affects the biology of ApoE4/E4 organoids while having only a minor impact on ApoE3/E3 organoids. This observation is in excellent agreement with the *in vitro* HDX-MS experiments (Fig. 3A). As shown in Fig. 6C, the transcriptomic data, adjusted for technical confounders (Figure S16A), was used for clustering and resulted in a distinct separation between ApoE3/E3 and ApoE4/E4 COs (Fig. 6C). Treatment with TRN only had a significant effect on homozygotic COs bearing the ApoE4 allele, which is the first genetic risk factor for late-onset AD [2]. This was further validated by a higher proportion of non-null tests for treatment comparisons within ApoE4/E4 COs compared to ApoE3/E3 COs (Fig. 6D; Table S6). Interestingly, although TRN did not explicitly regulate a specific pathway, it induced a notable shift in the expression of over 200 genes, bringing gene expression of ApoE4/E4 COs closer to that of ApoE3/E3 COs ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 6E, Figures S16C–D, Tables S6–8).

A similar expression trend was observed with TMP treatment [5], acting here as a positive control, with several of the identified genes associated with neurodevelopment, autophagy pathways, or lipid metabolism (Figure S17, list of genes related to individual pathways is listed in Table S7). Importantly, similar upregulation trend was observed on the protein level by mass spectrometry, although it did not reach full statistical significance (Fig. 6F), as shown by selected proteins related to neuronal development (PAX6, NES, MAP2) and lipid

metabolism (CLU). Collectively, our data suggest that TRN can significantly modulate gene expression in ApoE4/E4 organoids, aligning it more closely with the gene expression profile of ApoE3/E3, particularly in genes linked to neurodevelopment, lipid metabolism, and autophagy, all pathways previously connected to AD pathogenesis.

4. Discussion

The ‘‘ApoE Cascade Hypothesis’’ stipulates that the aggregation of ApoE would play an important role in neurodegeneration [2]. Indeed, different ApoE isoforms, as well as defects in ApoE levels, oligomerization and lipidation states, are involved in many ApoE-related pathologies, such as AD, PD, LBD, macular degeneration, and polycystic ovary syndrome [49]. ApoE is mostly lipidated [50], and a lack of lipidation is correlated with increased A β aggregation *in vivo*. ApoE4 is the least-lipidated, the most aggregation-prone isoform, and a genetic risk factor for late-onset AD, PD, and LBD. Conversely, ApoE3 and ApoE2 are less aggregation-prone and more lipidated [2,4]. In the case of AD, ApoE binds to toxic A β fibrils, and inhibits their elongation [51]. A notable exception occurs in the context of macular degeneration, where ApoE2 is a genetic risk factor and ApoE4 is protective [3].

ApoE3 and ApoE4 differ by a single mutation, C112R. The effect of this mutation is profound in ApoE4 T-shaped dimers, in which the R61-E109 interaction is lost, and Q123 changes conformation, leading to the destabilization and bending of helix 3 [5]. In our previous study, we showed that TMP can directly inhibit ApoE4 aggregation *in vitro* using purified proteins and strongly affect lipid compositions *in vivo* in COs. However, TMP is metabolized *in vivo* into SPA, suppressing ApoE4 aggregation even more efficiently [5]. In this study, we focused on studying the effect of TRN, a close structural analogue of TMP. TRN is an abundant amino acid produced in the liver and the central nervous system [6]. However, its interaction with ApoE has remained largely unexplored.

The weak binding observed for TRN is consistent with a distributed, multivalent mechanism rather than a high-affinity 1:1 interaction

Fig. 6. Effects of TRN treatment on COs. (A) Schematic representation of experimental design. (B) Paraffin sections from D100 organoids show overall morphology and representative staining of neuronal and glial markers. Left scale bar: 500 μm , right scale bar: 150 μm . (C-D) Characterization of transcriptomic data based on next-generation sequencing screening (mRNA sequencing) of non-treated control COs (NTR) and COs treated with TRN. (C) Multidimensional scaling. (D) Proportions of non-null tests (π_1) for various scenarios. Higher estimates indicate more significant differences. (E) LogFoldChange expression of genes differentially expressed in between *ApoE4/ApoE3* genotypes ($p\text{-adj} < 0.1$, $\text{abs}(\log_2\text{FCH}) > 0.6$; $n = 206$) and their shift in expression after TRN treatment ($p < 0.001$; $n = 104$). *Left*: down-regulated genes in ApoE4 compared to ApoE3 and shift of their expression toward the ApoE3 after the TRN treatment ($p < 0.001$; $n = 104$). *Right*: up-regulated genes in ApoE4 compared to ApoE3 and shift of their expression toward the ApoE3 after the TRN treatment ($p < 0.0001$; $n = 102$). (F) Changes in protein levels involved in neurodevelopment (PAX6, NES, MAP2) and lipid metabolism (CLU) as a function of genotype and TRN treatment. NTR *ApoE3/ApoE3* COs protein level is defined as 1. Protein abundances were normalized within each genotype to the corresponding non-treated (NTR) control, and therefore, NTR values are displayed as 1. Each dot represents one organoid, $n = 15\text{--}16$ organoids from three independent batches (5–6 organoids per batch) were analyzed and are visualized here. Statistical significance between TRN vs NTR within each genotype was assessed using a *t*-test; ns, not significant.

(Figures S6–8, Table S4). This aligns with prior analyses of TMP with A β 42, where multiple ligand molecules bind A β monomers to suppress aggregation [52]. Computational and experimental studies also support predominantly nonspecific interactions for TMP and SPA, stabilizing less aggregation-prone conformations of A β [53]. Our recent work indicates that TRN and SPA interactions with ApoE follow a similar mode, with weak, distributed interactions across multiple sites modulating ApoE conformation and aggregation propensity [5]. The millimolar $K_{D,\text{app}}$

values obtained here further support a multivalent interaction mechanism also for TRN. Notably, SLS data demonstrate that these interactions reduce aggregate formation and can partially dissociate pre-formed aggregates, particularly for ApoE4.

We showed that TRN inhibits ApoE4 aggregation with an efficiency comparable to SPA (Fig. 4) and that the TRN-ApoE4 interaction, similarly to SPA-ApoE4, alters the local flexibility of ApoE4 (Fig. 5). MD simulations were conducted using the NTD domain, as the CTD domain

is, in the absence of lipids, highly dynamic and poorly structured. The simulations indicate that TRN can destabilize dimers and reduce aggregation propensity, with a similar efficiency as SPA (Fig. 2A, Fig. 3A). These effects appear to arise from a network of weak electrostatic interactions between the small molecules and the specific protein residues, which compete with electrostatically driven ApoE dimerization, thereby modulating its aggregation propensity (Fig. 2B-C). Since the structure of ApoE dimers remained incompletely resolved, we employed VAMP clustering on association adaptive goal MD simulations that identified four structurally distinct dimer conformations: (i) V-shaped, (ii) T-shaped, (iii) parallel, and (iv) anti-T-shaped. Except for the anti-T-shaped dimers, the other three were observed in the crystallographic lattice of the available ApoE N-domain crystal structures [5]. However, the anti-T-shaped dimer offers a novel perspective on the differences between ApoE3 and ApoE4. Notably, the single mutation C112R contributes to the dimerization interface in this model, unlike the other dimer types. It is important to emphasize that the anti-T-shaped dimer is based on MD simulations and requires experimental validation. We should note that these observations were obtained from simulations of dimeric ApoE NTD structures, which reflect only partially the interactions of the small molecules occurring in the full-length proteins. Therefore, these results should be interpreted with caution. The CTD makes a crucial contribution to higher-order oligomerization and lipid interactions. Furthermore, its presence in the full-length protein may also sterically hinder or alter the TRN and SPA binding regions identified here, potentially modulating their anti-aggregation effects. Nevertheless, the NTD is the site where the critical C112/R112 polymorphism occurs. Because the stability and self-association of this domain are key drivers of the biophysical differences between ApoE3 and ApoE4, these simulations provide important mechanistic evidence of how small molecules can directly influence NTD dimer dynamics. Further simulations involving full-length ApoE systems, while complex and demanding, would be essential to confirm these interactions in a more complete molecular environment.

HDX-MS data support an ApoE4-specific increase in local flexibility within the NTD helix bundle, including regions adjacent to the C112R site, and show that both SPA and TRN partially reverse this effect by increasing backbone protection across multiple N-terminal elements while also extending protection into hinge and CTD segments implicated in self-association, as shown in Fig. 5. Rather than defining a single binding pocket, the distributed RFU decreases are most consistent with weak, surface-driven ligand engagement and or ligand-induced redistribution of conformational and oligomeric equilibria coupled to allosteric changes, an interpretation aligned with SPA and tramiprosate studies and HDX mapping of ApoE self-association [5,54]. Importantly, ApoE HDX signatures are highly context dependent; isoform differences are segment-localized and sensitive to self-association state, and labeling temperature. Lower temperatures stabilize frayed helix ends and attenuate fast motions [55], whereas some small-molecule HDX studies were performed at 25 °C to maximize contrast [56]. This context dependence is further supported by kinetic HDX-MS quantification of pronounced conformational heterogeneity and mixed EX1 and EX2 behavior in ApoE4 [57], as well as by the established interpretation of EX1 as slow structural opening [58]. Collectively, our results extend prior work by demonstrating that ApoE4-selective, ensemble-level stabilization, spanning both NTD helices and oligomerization-coupled CTD segments, is associated with reduced aggregation.

At the cellular level, the data collected with COs show that TRN specifically affected the biology of ApoE4/E4 organoids, with only a minimal impact on ApoE3/E3 organoids (Fig. 6). Analogous observation has been made in our previous study with COs and TMP [5]. TRN induced a shift in the expression of over 200 genes, bringing the gene expression profile of ApoE4/E4 organoids closer to that of ApoE3/E3 organoids. Several of the identified differentially expressed genes were associated with neurodevelopment, autophagy pathways, or lipid metabolism, some of these trends were further supported using MS

protein analysis. Indeed, it has previously been suggested that TRN has neuroprotective effects [59], immunomodulatory effects [60–62], and the ability to activate autophagy [63]. In the context of AD, TRN has been shown to protect neurons against excitotoxicity induced by A β *in vitro* [64], to recover spatial memory in the APP/PS1 mouse model [65] and to improve glutamatergic activity in the brain of the 5xFAD mouse model [66]. Our data on COs are in line with published observations and indicate that TRN effects are specific to ApoE4 and not ApoE3. This further supports the notion that TRN, like TMP and SPA, can correct the structure, oligomerization state, aggregation propensity, and biological functions of ApoE4, shifting them closer to those of ApoE3 [5].

It should be noted that taurine was applied at 100 μ M in organoid experiments over a prolonged 50-day treatment period to ensure cellular viability, whereas millimolar concentrations were required to observe effects in biophysical assays, consistent with its weak, multivalent binding mode; therefore, direct translation between these systems should be made with caution.

In summary, TRN interacts with ApoE4 to modulate its aggregation behavior (Fig. 7) and thus may influence ApoE4-associated molecular pathways linked to neurodegeneration [67]. A notable similarity was observed in the effects of SPA and TRN at the molecular and cellular levels, as these molecules induce changes in ApoE4 that shift its properties toward those observed for ApoE3, including effects on conformation, aggregation propensity, and associated molecular signatures. Dietary supplementation with TRN has already been proposed as a therapeutic strategy for addressing TRN deficiency in various pathological conditions [68]. Our study underscores the potential of TRN as a promising therapeutic agent for neurodegenerative diseases associated with ApoE aggregation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jiri Damborsky: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Stanislav Mazurenko:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Marketa Nezvedova:** Formal analysis. **Jiri Sedlar:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Cerna Katerina:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Sergio Marques:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Martin Marek:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Josef Sivic:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Anthony Legrand:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Lenka Hernychova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Prokop Zbyněk:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration,

Fig. 7. Anti-ApoE aggregation and neuroprotective properties of taurine and its derivatives. TRN-based treatment can help in preventing ApoE aggregation through direct interaction, and in promoting neuron development, lysosomal autophagy (this study), and putative neuroprotection and anti-inflammatory properties [67].

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